

THE ROLE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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Abstract. At present, time is developing intensely and in today's globalized world, intercultural communication has become a crucial part of personal, academic, and professional companionship. For this reason, foreign languages are considered to be as an essential instrument in facilitating mutual understanding among representatives of different cultures. The following research explores the role of foreign languages in enhancing intercultural dialogue, overcoming communication barriers, and encouraging worldwide unity. Moreover, it emphasizes the cognitive and social benefits of multilingualism in multicultural environments.

Keywords: foreign languages, intercultural communication, globalization, multilingualism, cultural understanding, communication barriers, multicultural environment.

Аннотация. Сейчас время очень быстро развивается, и в современном глобализированном мире межкультурная коммуникация стала важнейшей частью личного, академического и профессионального общения. По этой причине иностранные языки рассматриваются как важнейший инструмент, способствующий взаимопониманию между представителями разных культур. В данном исследовании рассматривается роль иностранных языков в развитии межкультурного диалога, преодолении коммуникационных барьеров и укреплении мирового единства. Кроме того, в нем подчеркиваются когнитивные и социальные преимущества многоязычия в поликультурной среде.

Ключивые слова: иностранные языки, межкультурная коммуникация, глобализация, многоязычие, культурное взаимопонимание, коммуникационные барьеры, мультикультурная среда.

Annotatsiya. Hozirda zamon shiddat bilan rivojlanib bormoqda va bugungi globallashtirilgan dunyoda madaniyalararo muloqot shaxsiy, akademik va kasbiy hamkorlikning o'ta muhim qismiga aylandi. Shu sababdan xorijiy tillar turli madaniyat vakillarining o'zaro tushunushlarini osonlashtiradigan o'ta muhim ko'rsatkich hisoblanadi. Quyidagi ma'lumotlar xorijiy tillarni millatlararo muloqotning sifatini yaxshilashda, muloqot to'siqlarini yengishda va birlikni yanada mustahkamlashdagi ahamiyatini ko'rsatadi. Shuningdek, unda ko'p millatli muhitda bir nechta tillarni bilishning aqliy va ijtimoiy foydalarini ham ta'kidlab o'tiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: xorijiy tillar, madaniyatlararo muloqot, globallashtirish, ko'p tillilik, madaniyatlararo o'zaro tushunish, muloqot to'siqlari, ko'p madaniyatli muhit.

Introduction

This 100-year period has seen a significant rise in intercultural interactions because of globalization, migration, international business, and digital communication. In these mentioned spheres, foreign language skills have become more important than ever, as speaking a second language gives an opportunity to engage with a wider network of partners and clients. Language proficiency is not only a means of verbal exchange but also a key to understanding cultural values, traditions and thoughts (Gulomova, 2020).

Language is a tool of cultural understanding

Language skills play a crucial role in breaking down barriers in cross-cultural communication and they provide access to different worldviews. Therefore, it is the primary tool which we use to describe our thoughts, feelings, and ideas to others. Learning about the linguistic nuances of another culture can help understand more deeply their values, beliefs, and traditions. This an effective way of avoiding misunderstandings and misinterpretations that can arise from differences in language or cultural norms.

Practical benefits in global contexts

Proficiency in the language is highly valued in most spheres, as in international business, diplomacy, education, tourism and others. The benefits of language knowledge in international business are that communicating with a partner the same language fosters trust and respect and reduces the risk of misunderstanding

In education language skills give an opportunity to be aware of global knowledge as well as to participate in international conferences and exchange knowledge

In tourism are that it provides a wide range of opportunities, as better custom service, wider career opportunities, effective marketing, cultural, understanding, problem resolution, improved communication with tourists, better customer service.

Cognitive and social advantages

Studies show that multilingual individuals usually have better cognitive flexibility and social skills. They are capable of enhancing mental flexibility, making better decisions, having greater cultural sensitivity and stronger interpersonal connections.

Conclusion

To sum up, foreign languages play a vital role in facilitating effective communication among the individuals who belong to diverse cultural backgrounds. They serve as an important tool which assists to overcome language barriers, enhance cultural understanding, build trust and respect, support global collaboration, promote inclusivity, reduce stereotypes and prejudice.

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